

Étude ma vie et la
pandémie au
Québec

METHODES

Methodological report

Questionnaires

November, 22th 2022 Version

**« Ma vie avec la pandémie au Québec – MAVIPAN »
Living with the pandemic in Quebec – MAVIPAN**

Methodological document – Questionnaires section

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And its partners
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Context

The Living with the pandemic (MAVIPAN – Ma vie avec la pandémie) study was launched as a collective effort to bring together the 4 research centers of the CIUSSS de la Capitale-Nationale, namely: CIRRIIS Center for Interdisciplinary Research in Rehabilitation and Social Integration, CRUJeF University Research Center for Youth and Families, CERVO Research Center, and VITAM Centre de recherche en santé durable, with the support of Université Laval's PULSAR collaborative research platform.

It is intended to be an initiative designed to support the research community and to serve as a public health information tool.

MAVIPAN is supported by a group of researchers, partners and collaborators. The complete list is available at www.mavipan.ca

Caution

This methodological document was written for MAVIPAN's researchers and collaborators. It is made available before the end of the study while several data collections are ongoing or planned. The information provided in this document is subject to change pending study progress. Updated versions will be released periodically in the coming months and years. If you have any concerns regarding information in this document, we suggest you contact the study's team at mavipan.ciusscn@ssss.gouv.qc.ca

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. DATA COLLECTION	5
1.1 Distribution of questionnaires	5
1.2 Sample size	9
1.3 Follow-up questionnaires	11
1.4 Participant withdrawal	16
2. THEMES AND QUESTIONNAIRE ORGANIZATION	17
3. BASELINE QUESTIONNAIRE, VERSION 1 & 2	22
3.1 Questionnaire structure	22
3.2 Definition of populations (sub-cohorts)	23
3.3 Indicators and populations (commented)	24
4. MENTAL HEALTH FOLLOW-UPS QUESTIONNAIRE	49
4.1 Structure of the questionnaire	49
4.2 Definition of populations (sub-cohorts)	50
4.3 Indicators and populations (commented)	51
5. QUESTIONNAIRE AD HOC 1 DECEMBER 2020	57
5.1 Structure of the questionnaire	57
5.2 Definition of populations (sub-cohorts)	57
5.3 Groups of participants according to the date on which they answered the baseline questionnaire	58
5.4 Indicators and populations (commented)	60
6. AD HOC 2 (MAY 2021) AND AD HOC 3 (MAY 2022) QUESTIONNAIRES	66
6.1 Questionnaire structure	66
6.2 Population définition (sub-cohorts)	66
6.3 Population indicators (commented)	69
7. REFERENCES OF VALIDATED SCALES AND INDICATORS	92
8. CONTACTS	95

1. DATA COLLECTION

1.1 Distribution of questionnaires

Table 1 Distribution and closing dates of questionnaires.

Questionnaire	Distribution	Closing	Comments
Baseline questionnaires			
Version 1	29/04/2020 (FR)	26/07/2020	Participants could sign up until 20/07/2020 and had 7 days to complete the questionnaire. This questionnaire refers to, in terms of temporality, the time “before the pandemic/confinement measures”.
	22/05/2020 (EN)		
Version 2	29/07/2020	19/07/2020	Compared to version 1, the following modifications were made: (i) Temporality: questions regarding temporality now refer to the month or the week prior (no longer to a time “before the pandemic”; (ii) some questions referring to the situation before the pandemic were removed.
Mental health follow-up questionnaires			
Follow-up 1 (June 2020)	18/06/2020	25/06/2020	French only
Follow-up 2 (October 2020)	21/10/2020	28/10/2020	N/A
Follow-up 3 (February 2021)	15/02/2021 (FR)	26/02/2021 (FR)	Due to emailing issues, participants exceptionally had 10 days to complete this questionnaire.
	16/02/2021 (EN)	27/02/2021 (EN)	
Follow-up 4 (September 2021)	31/08/2021	08/09/2021	Due to emailing issues, the invitations were sent out on two days (August 31 st and September 1 st) but each participant had 7 days to complete the questionnaire.
Follow-up 5 (February 2022)	21/02/2022	28/02/2022	N/A
Follow-up 6 (September 2022)	26/09/2022	03/10/2022	N/A

Ad Hoc thematic questionnaires			
Ad Hoc 1 (December 2020)	10/12/2020	17/12/2020	N/A
Ad Hoc 2 (May 2021)	10/05/2021	17/05/2021	N/A
Ad Hoc 3 (May 2022)	09/05/2022	17-05-2022	Due to technical reasons, participants have had up to 8 days to complete the questionnaire for technical reasons

Figure 1 : Diagram of questionnaire distribution amongst the different arms^{1,2}

*** Registrations ended on July 19th, 2021. Arm 6 is the last study arm. From then on, all participants are invited to complete the follow-up questionnaires.**

¹ Here, the arms indicate a specific group of participants who have been asked to complete the same questionnaires list.

² The N of the different arms in the figure may differ from the actual N of the study.

Table 2 : Invitations to participate in the various questionnaires according to the date of participation to the baseline questionnaire.

Study arm	Baseline questionnaire completion date	Follow-up 1 (June 2020)	Follow-up 2 (Oct. 2020)	Ad Hoc 1 (Dec. 2020)	Follow-up 3 (Feb. 2021)	Ad Hoc 2 (May 2021)	Quest. sent as of August 2021
1	29/04/2020 to 10/05/2020	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
2	11/05/2020 to 15/09/2020		Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
3	16/09/2020 to 23/11/2020			Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
4	24/11/2020 to 15/01/2021				Yes	Yes	Yes
5	16/01/2021 to 10/04/2021					Yes	Yes
6	11/04/2021 to 19/07/2021						Yes

1.2 Sample size

We have a non-probabilistic sample associated to an online sampling and a snowballing technique of unrestricted size. Based on the recruitment rate to date, we expect to recruit 5,000 participants by the end of 2021 and 7,500 participants by the end of the study.

We recognize the biases and limitations associated with this sampling technique (e.g., sampling error, lack of population representation). We have included key socio-demographic questions that will allow us to compare and to weigh the data according to provincial and national standards. We have used questions validated by key institutions such as Statistics Canada to increase the comparability of our results.

1.2.1 Sample size for the baseline questionnaire

Table 3 : Baseline questionnaire – Final table

Baseline questionnaire version	Initial sample size (registered participants)	Withdrawal with data deletion	Exclusion factors		Final sample
			People living outside Quebec*	Missing data on age or place of residence**	
BASELINE 1 – April 29, 2020 to July 24, 2020					
French	2653	6	11	22	2614
English	50	0	0	3	47
Sub-total	2703	6	11	25	2661
BASELINE 1 – July 29, 2020 to December 31, 2020					
French	144	0	0	4	140
English	11	0	0	0	11
Sub-total	155	0	0	4	151
BASELINE 1 – January 1, 2021 July 19, 2021					
French	377	0	0	7	370
English	5	0	0	0	5
Sub-total	382	0	0	7	375
COMBINED QUESTIONNAIRE (BASELINE 1 & 2) – April 29, 2020 to July 29, 2021					
French	3174	6	11	33	3126
English	66	0	0	3	63
Sub-total	3240	6	11	36	3187

* Participants are excluded if they indicate living outside the province of Quebec (reg1 = 100).

** If participants do not indicate their region of residence or age at the beginning of the questionnaire (MAVIPAN questionnaire) they are excluded from the database as we cannot validate these inclusion criteria.

1.3 Follow-up questionnaires

Table 4 : Mental health follow-up questionnaires

Version	Dates	Initial eligible sample (number of invitations sent)	Withdrawal with data deletion	Final sample	Final sample (participants having completed the questionnaire at least partially)
Follow-up 1 (June 2020)					
French only	18/06/2020-25/06/2020	1009	2	1007	530
Follow-up 2 (October 2020)					
French	21/10/2020-28/10/2020	2686	1	2685	1608
English	21/10/2020-28/10/2020	60	0	60	36
Combined	21/10/2020-28/10/2020	2746	0	2745	1644
Follow-up 3 (February 2021)					
French	15/02/2021-26/02/2021	2797	0	2797	1223
English	16/02/2021-27/02/2021	61	0	61	29
Combined	15/02/2021-27/02/2021	2858	0	2858	1252
Follow-up 4 (September 2021)					
French	01/09/2021-08/09/2021	3142	0	3142	1329
English	01/09/2021-08/09/2021	65	0	65	22
Combined	01/09/2021-08/09/2021	3207 ³	0	3207	1351

Follow-up 5 (February 2022)					
French	21/02/2022- 28/02/2022	3124	0	3122	1341
English	21/02/2022- 28/02/2022	65	0	65	23
Combined	21/02/2022- 28/02/2022	3207	0	3207	1364
Follow-up 6 (September 2022)					
French	26/09/2022- 03/10/2022	3122	0	3122	1127
English	26/09/2022- 03/10/2022	65	0	65	22
Combined	26/09/2022- 03/10/2022	3187	0	3187	1149

Table 5 : Ad Hoc Questionnaires

Version	Dates	Initial eligible sample (number of invitations sent)	Withdrawal with data deletion	Final sample	Final sample (participants having completed the questionnaire at least partially)
Adhoc 1 Questionnaire (December 2020)					
French	10/12/2020-17/12/2020	2736	1	2735	1303
English	10/12/2020-17/12/2020	61	0	61	26
Combined	10/12/2020-17/12/2020	2797	1	2796	1329
Adhoc 2 Questionnaire (May 2021)					
French	10/05/2021-17/05/2021	2937	0	2937	1335
English	10/05/2021-17/05/2021	62	0	62	27
Combined	10/05/2021-17/05/2021	2999	0	2999	1362
Adhoc 3 Questionnaire (May 2022)					
French	09/05/2022-17/05/2022	3139	02	3137	1173
English	09/05/2022-17/05/2022	65	0	65	21
Combined	09/05/2022-17/05/2022	3204	2	3202	1194

Tableau 1 : Sample sizes for questionnaire combinations

Complete baseline questionnaire	Follow-up 1 (June 2020)	Follow-up 1 (Oct.2020)	Ad Hoc 1 (Dec. 2020)	Follow-up 2 (Feb. 2021)	Adhoc 2 (May 2021)	Follow-up 4 (Sep. 2021)	Follow-up 5 (Feb. 2022)	Adhoc 3 (May 2022)	Follow-up 6 (sept 2022)	N
X	X									529
X	X	X								420
X	X	X	X							309
X	X	X	X	X						252
X	X	X	X	X	X					226
X	X	X	X	X	X	X				203
X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X			180
X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		162
X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	138
X		X								1637
X			X							1322
X				X						1246
X					X					1354
X						X				1345
X							X			1356
X								X		1186
X									X	1142
X		X		X						1023
X		X		X		X				774
X		X		X		X	X			656
	X		X		X		X	X		518

Complete baseline questionnaire	Follow-up 1 (June 2020)	Follow-up 1 (Oct.2020)	Ad Hoc 1 (Dec. 2020)	Follow-up 2 (Feb. 2021)	Adhoc 2 (May 2021)	Follow-up 4 (Sep. 2021)	Follow-up 5 (Feb. 2022)	Adhoc 3 (May 2022)	Follow-up 6 (sept 2022)	N
X		X	X							1074
X		X	X	X						812
X		X	X	X	X					695
X		X	X	X	X	X				586
X		X	X	X	X	X	X			510
X		X	X	X	X	X	X	X		440
X		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	378
X			X		X					932
X			X		X			X		649

1.4 Participant withdrawal

Table 6: Monitoring participant withdrawal requests.

Period	With data deletion	Without data deletion (invitations ceased only)
July 1st – December 31st 2020	4	6
January 1st – June 30th 2021	0	8
July 31st - December 31st 2021	0	6
January 1st – June 30th 2022	2	4
January 1st – June 30th 2022	0	6
TOTAL	6	30

2. THEMES AND QUESTIONNAIRE ORGANIZATION

The diagrams on the following pages (Summary of measures) summarize the main themes covered in the baseline questionnaires 1 and 2, follow-ups and the Ad Hoc 1 questionnaire. The information is presented conceptually and not according to the question order in the questionnaire. The specific content of each questionnaire is detailed in the following sections.

Each questionnaire is divided into thematic forms allowing to group questions regarding the same topic or that are intended for a specific population. The list of forms and the themes covered are presented for each questionnaire.

A table summarizing the targeted populations is also presented. It indicates the variables that were used to identify the sub-cohorts. For example, people with disabilities, the elderly, etc.

Finally, the last table presents *the indicators measured within each form*. In addition, the list of indicators contains their variable name, any possible sub-populations, as well as comments on the transformations to be made or already conducted.

The questionnaires and the codification of the detailed variables (particularly response choices) are available in separate documents

SUMMARY OF MEASURES

Baseline Questionnaire (version 1 & 2)

General indicators

HEALTH DETERMINANTS

Health antecedents

- Perceived physical health
- Perceived mental health
- Satisfaction with life
- Physical chronic illness diagnoses
- Mental health disorders and diagnoses
- Disabilities
- Anthropometric measurements
- Advance care planning

COVID-19 exposure

- Exposure to COVID-19
- COVID-19 diagnosis

SOCIAL AND BEHAVIORAL DETERMINANTS

Social and behavioral indicators

- Social support
- Altruistic behaviour
- Coping strategies
- Physical exercise and leisure activities

INDIVIDUAL DETERMINANTS

Demographic, social and economic indicators

- Age and gender
- Socio-economic status
- Household composition
- Dependents
- Immigration status
- Employment status (essential worker, working from home)
- Loved one in a long-term care home
- Dwelling characteristics

Geographic indicators

- Region
- Rural, peri-urban or urban area
- Neighborhood (in urban areas)

PSYCHOSOCIAL IMPACT

Psychosocial impact indicators

- Perceived physical health
- Perceived mental health
- Satisfaction with life
- Wellbeing
- Stress, depression and anxiety symptoms
- Sleep quality
- Loneliness
- Hostility
- Food consumption, tobacco and drug use
- Fears about seeking health or social care services
- Testimonies: lived experiences

Specific indicators for vulnerable populations

<p>Young people 14-17</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relationships in foster home or youth centre 	<p>Families</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Partner and ex-partner relationships • Children's behavior • Behavior towards children 	<p>People living with chronic illnesses</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Medication observance/adherence • Ability to get one's prescribed medication 	<p>People living with mental health conditions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Medication observance/adherence • Ability to get one's prescribed medication 	<p>People with disabilities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Impact of the quality of the living environment • Lifestyle habits 	<p>Natural caregivers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Role and relationship with person being cared for • Experience of lockdown (for carers of children) 	<p>Healthcare and soc. serv. system stakeholders</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Working conditions, fatigue • Job perception • Concern, needs • Factors for well-being
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SUMMARY OF MEASURES

Mental Health Follow-ups

General indicators

HEALTH DETERMINANTS

Health antecedents

- --

COVID-19 exposure

- COVID-19 diagnosis

SOCIAL AND BEHAVIORAL DETERMINANTS

Social and behavioral indicators

- Social support
- Physical exercise and leisure activities

PSYCHOSOCIAL IMPACT

Psychosocial impact indicators

- Perceived physical health
- Perceived mental health
- Satisfaction with life
- Wellbeing
- Stress, depression and anxiety symptoms
- Sleep quality
- Loneliness
- Hostility
- Food consumption, tobacco and drug use
- Fears related to the end of sanitary restriction measures
- Happiness in couple relationship
- Burnout
- Testimonies : lived experiences

INDIVIDUAL DETERMINANTS

Demographic, social and economic indicators

- Age
- Relationship status
- Employment status (essential worker)

Geographic indicators

- Region

Specific indicators for vulnerable populations

SUMMARY OF MEASURES

Ad Hoc Questionnaire 1 - December 2020

General indicators

HEALTH DETERMINANTS

- Public health measures**
- Individual perceptions about the public health measures adopted by the government in response to the COVID-19 crisis

SOCIAL AND BEHAVIORAL DETERMINANTS

- Social and behavioral indicators**
- Work-life balance
 - Work-study-personal life balance (for minors and students)
 - Concerns of young people regarding education and employment

INDIVIDUAL DETERMINANTS

- Demographic, social and economic indicators**
- Age
 - Socio-economic status
 - Household composition
 - Dwelling characteristics
 - Employment area
 - Schedule and workload
 - Sedentarity at work
 - Work from home
 - Internet access and use
- Geographic indicators**
- Region
 - Metropolitan region

PSYCHOSOCIAL IMPACT

- Psychosocial impact indicators**
- Behavioral difficulties affecting activities and interpersonal relationships
 - Parental stress
 - Quality of childrens' relationships with their parents
 - Resilience

Specific indicators for vulnerable populations

<p>Young people 14-17</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • -- 	<p>Families</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • -- 	<p>People living with chronic illnesses</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • -- 	<p>People living with mental health conditions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • -- 	<p>People with disabilities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • -- 	<p>Natural caregivers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • -- 	<p>Healthcare and soc. serv. system stakeholders</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • --
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SUMMARY OF MEASURES

Ad Hoc Questionnaire 2 - May 2022 and after

General indicators

HEALTH DETERMINANTS

Health antecedents

- Mental health disorders and diagnoses
- Physical chronic disorder diagnoses
- Disabilities
- Anthropometric measurements

Reduction in healthcare activities

- Use of and access to usual healthcare services
- Use of and access to healthcare services during the pandemic

SOCIAL AND BEHAVIORAL DETERMINANTS

Social and behavioral indicators

- Social support
- Coping strategies
- Work-study-personal life balance (for minors and students)
- Young people's concerns about education and employment

PSYCHOSOCIAL IMPACT

Psychosocial impact indicators

- Resilience
- Post-traumatic growth
- Appraisal and ambivalence one year into the pandemic

INDIVIDUAL DETERMINANTS

Demographic, social and economic indicators

- Age and gender
- Socio-economic status
- Household composition
- Dependants
- Immigration status
- Employment status (essential worker, working from home)
- Loved one in a long-term care home
- Dwelling characteristics

Geographic indicators

- Region
- Rural, peri-urban or urban area
- Neighborhood (in urban areas)

Specific indicators for vulnerable populations

Young people 14-17

- (Ad hoc 2 only)*
- Relationships in foster home or youth centre

Families

- Partner and ex-partner relationships
- Children's behavior
- Behavior towards children

People living with chronic illnesses

- Medication observance/adherence
- Ability to get one's prescribed medication

People living with mental health conditions

- Medication observance/adherence
- Ability to get one's prescribed medication

People with disabilities

- Impact of the quality of the living environment
- Lifestyle habits

Natural caregivers

- Role and relationship with person being cared for
- Carers for children

Healthcare and soc. serv. system stakeholders

- Working conditions, fatigue
- Job perception
- Concern, needs
- Factors for well-being

3. BASELINE QUESTIONNAIRE, VERSION 1 & 2

3.1 Questionnaire structure

SECTION	POPULATION	PAGE
CORE		
Eligibility and sociodemographic status	All	24
Employment situation	All	25
Health status	All	26
Well-being	All	27
Emotional health	All	27
Social support	All	28
COVID-19 exposure	All	29
Palliative care	All	30
Physical and leisure activities, consumption profiles	All	30
Additional information	All	32
Income	All	33
SUB-COHORTS		
Couple relationship	Participants in a relationship	33
Separated parents	Separated parents	33
Children's health	Adults living with children, including step-parents	36
Foster families	Foster families	38
Chronic illnesses management	Participants with a chronic illness or a mental health disorder	39
Caregivers	Caregivers	40
Participants 14 to 17 years old	Youths living in a group home or a rehabilitation center	42
Quality of the environment	Individuals with disabilities	42
Life habits	Individuals with disabilities	44
Life habits since the lockdown	Individuals with disabilities	44
Health and social services workers	Health and social services workers	47
Final questions	All	48

3.2 Definition of populations (sub-cohorts)

Population	Description	Identification variables
All (all populations below are sub-populations of this group)	Population living in Quebec	[reg1] <> '100'
Elderly	65 years old and over	age1>64
Adults	18 years old and over	age1≥18
Youths	14-17 years old	age1<18
Chronic physical or mental illness	Populations with chronic diseases or mental health disorders	(([asan1(1)] = true or [asan1(2)] = true or [asan1(3)] = true or [asan1(4)] = true or [asan1(5)] = true or [asan1(6)] = true or [asan1(7)] = true or [asan1(8)] = true or [asan1(9)] = true or [asan1(10)] = true or [asan1(11)] = true or ([asan8] = 1 and [asan6] = 1))
Disabilities	People with one or more persistent disabilities	(([asan2] = 1 or [asan3(10)] = true)
People in a couple relationship	People in a couple relationship, living or not with their partner	(([soc5] = 2 OR [soc5] = 1) and [age1] > 17
Separated parents	People with children but no longer in a couple relationship with the other parent	[soc8(2)] = true and [age1] > 17
Step-parents	People living with the children from their partner's previous union	[soc8(3)] = true and [age1] > 17
Adults living with children	Adults living with one or more children under 18 years old (being their parent or not)	(([soc6] = 1) and [age1] >17
Foster parents	Adults caring for foster children	(([soc8(4)] =true) and [age1] >17
Caregivers	Adults in a caregiving role	[cha1] = 1 and [age1] > 17
RSSS actors	Actors working in the health and social services network	[age1] > 17 and [emp1] = 1 and (([emp3] = 1 or [emp3] = 2 or [emp3] = 3)

3.3 Indicators and populations (commented)

The following tables describe indicators measured in MAVIPAN and provide additional information for their use. This is not an exhaustive list of the variables measured in the project (for this, please refer to the questionnaires) but a list of the main indicators. Thus, the indicators presented here may include one or more variables.

- When the indicator is a scale, the list of variables is indicated between parentheses.
 - o For example, the DASS-21 scale (dass1 to dass21)
- Some indicators may include additional variables: these are not shown in this document.
 - o For example, some indicators contain a variable called "if other, please specify" not shown here. The labels of "other" variables are the same as their parent variable with an "a" at the end (e.g., log7a).

Section - MAVIPAN

Variable name	Label	Targeted population	Additional rules	Comments
Region of residence	reg1	All		
Participant age	age1	All		
Participant gender	sex1	All		
Number of rooms in the dwelling	log1	All		
Number of people living in the dwelling	log2	All		
Type of dwelling since lockdown	log5	All		
Change of dwelling since the start of lockdown	log6	Elderly		
Type of dwelling before lockdown	log7	Elderly	Change of dwelling since the start of the pandemic ([log6]=2)	Version 1 only
Presence of a pet	log4	All		

First three characters of the postal code	zip1	All	Text variable: beware of possible errors
Relationship status	soc5	Adults	
Presence of minor children in the dwelling	soc6	Adults	
Age of minor children	soc7 (soc71 to soc76)	Adults living with children	
Household composition	soc8	Adults living with children	
Single parent	soc10	Adults living with children	
Persons with special health needs under the participant's responsibility (caregiver)	cha1	Adults	
Number of children (<18 years old) with these special health needs	cha4	Caregivers	
Number of adults (18-64 years old) with these special health needs	cha5	Caregivers	
Number of adults (≥65 years old) with these special health needs	cha6	Caregivers	

Section - Employment situation

Variable name	Label	Targeted population	Additional rules	Comments
Highest education level	edu1	All		Adapted from Statistics Canada (CCHS 2011)

Attending school before lockdown started	edu2	All		
Actors of the health and social services network	emp1	Adults		
Main occupation before the start of lockdown	emp2	All		Version 1 only
Main occupation since the start of lockdown	emp3	All		
Essential service worker	emp5	All	If paid job ([emp3]=1 or 2 or 3)	According to the list of April 20, 2020 of the Government of Quebec
Job loss or main source of income in the near future	emp4	All	If paid job ([emp3]=1 or 2 or 3)	
Workplace since the lockdown (teleworking or usual place)	emp6	Adults	If paid job ([emp3]=1 or 2 or 3)	

Section - Health status

Variable name	Label	Targeted population	Additional rules	Comments
Perception of physical health	asan4	All		From Statistics Canada (CCHS 2011)
Perception of change in physical health status since the start of lockdown	isan1	All		Version 1 only Adapted from Statistics Canada (ESCC 2011)

Presence of significant and persistent impairments or disabilities	asan2	All	
Participant's types of chronic illnesses	asan1	All	
Perception of mental health	asan5	All	From Statistics Canada (ESCC 2011)
Perception of change in mental health since the start of lockdown	isan2	All	Version 1 only Adapted from Statistics Canada (ESCC 2011)
Presence of a mental health problem	asan8	All	
Participant's type of mental health problem	asan3	All	Presence of a mental health problem ([asan8]=1)
Physician diagnosis	asan6	All	Presence of a mental health problem ([asan8]=1)

Section - Well-being

Variable name	Label	Targeted population	Additional rules	Comments
Participant's satisfaction regarding their life during lockdown	sat1	All		From Statistics Canada (ESCC 2011)
Current life satisfaction compared to before lockdown	sat3	All		Version 1 only Adapted from Statistics Canada (ESCC 2011)
Participant's projected satisfaction with life in a year	sat2	All		Adapted from Statistics Canada (ESCC 2011)

Warwick-Edinburgh Wellbeing Scale	WEG (13 questions, weg1 to weg13)	All		From Tennant, et al. 2007 – Registered and authorized use of the scale. Use of registered and authorized scale. One question missing. We will use the shortened 7-item scale. From Version 2 onward , only these 7-items are used.
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Section - Emotional health

Variable name	Label	Targeted population	Additional rules	Comments
Number of hours of sleep before lockdown	som9	All		Version 1 only
Number of hours of sleep since lockdown	som10	All		
Insomnia Severity Index	som_etiquette (som1 to som7)	All		From Morin, 1997
Quality of sleep, compared to before lockdown	som8	All		Version 1 only
Depression Anxiety Stress Scale	DASS (21 questions, dass1 to dass21)	All		Lovibond and Lovibond, 1995)
Hostility scale	HOS (6 questions, hos1 to hos6)	All		Hostility subscale of Symptom Checklist-90 (Derogatis, 1994)

Section - Social support

Variable name	Label	Targeted population	Additional rules	Comments
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Social Provisions Scale	SSOC (10 questions, ssoc1 to ssoc10)	All	From Caron, 2013
Social support since the start of lockdown	Ssoc11	All	Version 1 only
Loneliness scale	SOL (4 questions, sol1 to sol4)	All	The questions come from the UCLA Loneliness Scale, but the choice of questions sol1, 2, 3 is based on Hugues, et al. 2004.
Presence of a relative in a long-term care facility (CHSLD) or private seniors' residence	exp1	All	
Frequency of social interactions with family or friends who are not confined with the participant, since the lockdown	ssoc12	All	Version 1 only
Perception of the frequency of these interactions	ssoc13	All	Version 1 only

Section – Exposure to COVID-19

Variable name	Label	Targeted population	Additional rules	Comments
Contact with a person who is likely or has been contaminated by COVID-19	exp3	All		

COVID-19 diagnosis in participant and types of symptoms by which they were having affected	exp4	All	
Participant hospitalization due to COVID-19	exp5	All	If severe or moderate symptoms ([exp4]=1 or 2)
Fear of consulting a doctor or being in a clinic or other medical setting	exp2	All	
Concerns regarding the gradual lifting of lockdown measures	exp7/exp7a, b, c, d, e, f	All	Version 1 only has exp7 (general fear regarding progressive lifting of lockdown measures). In Version 2 , exp7 has been split into several specific fears (exp7a to exp7f). The response options also differ between exp7 and exp7a to f.

Section – Palliative Care

Variable name	Label	Targeted population	Additional rules	Comments
Written instructions regarding desired level of care	pal1	Elderly		
Methods used to write medical wishes	pal2	Elderly	If medical wishes are written down ([pal1]=1)	

Section – Physical and leisure activities

Variable name	Label	Targeted population	Additional rules	Comments
Leisure time spent in front of a screen, per day, before and since lockdown	act1/act1_bis to act3	All		References to “before lockdown” have been removed from Version 2 for act1 to act 15. Consequently, act2 and act3 only exist in Version 1 . In addition, act1 has been renamed act1_bis in Version 2 . Note: The names of the variables in the baseline questionnaire and in the follow-ups do not match (e.g., act1_bis in Baseline 2 vs act1b in follow-ups 2 and 3)
Time spent walking, per day, before and since lockdown	act4/act4_bis to act6	All		Act5 and act6 only exist in Version 1 . Additionally, act4 has been renamed act4_bis in Version 2 .
Time spent in leisure cardiorespiratory-type physical activities, per week, before and since lockdown	act7/act7_bis to act9	All		Act8 and act9 only exist in Version 1 . Additionally, act7 has been renamed act7_bis in Version 2 .
Time spent in high intensity leisure cardiorespiratory-type physical activities, per week, before and since lockdown	act10/act10_bis to act12	All		Act11 and act12 only exist in Version 1 . Additionally, act10 has been renamed act10_bis in Version 2 .
Place where leisure physical activity was practiced before lockdown	act13/act13_bis /act13a_bis	All		Act13 has been renamed act13_bis in Version 2 . Act13a_bis (i.e. specify if other) only exists in Version 2 .
Types of physical activity done at home, before and since lockdown	act14_0/act14_0_bis, act14, act15	All		In Version 1 , act14_0 is just a title, the participant answers in act14 (before) and act15 (since lockdown). Version 2 only has act14_0_bis.
Consumption scale	CONS (14 questions,	All		Version 1 - From the COVID study by CH le Vinatier (Lyon, France)

	cons1 to cons14)		
Modified consumption scale	Cons7bis to 14, aliment1, cafe1, alcohol (3), tabac (2), vapotage (2) drogue1		Version 2 – certain questions kept, modification of certain answer options and new questions for alcohol, tobacco and vaping (see questionnaire)
Coping strategies: Brief Cope Scale	COP (16 questions, cop1 to cop16)	All	Adapted from Carver, et al. 2018 (Selected questions)
Altruism scale	ALT (5 questions, alt1 to alt5)	Adults	Adapted from Rushton, et al. 1991 (Selected questions)
Time spent keeping informed the COVID-19 crisis, per day	inf1	All	

Section - Additional information

Variable name	Label	Targeted population	Additional rules	Comments
Participant's marital status	soc4	Adults		From Statistics Canada 2016
Status in Canada	soc1	All		Adapted from Statistics Canada 2016
Indigenous identity	soc2	All		From Statistics Canada 2016
Ethnic or cultural identity	soc3	All		According to Statistics Canada classification (2017)
Participant's height	ant1	All		
Participant's weight	ant2	All		
Jeans or pants size	ant4 (men) and ant5 (women)	All		

Pregnancy in participant	fem1	All	Women ([sex1]=1)
If pregnant, number of weeks	fem2	All	Pregnant women ([fem1]=1)

Section - Income

Variable name	Label	Targeted population	Additional rules	Comments
Annual family income for 2019	rev1/rev1b	Adults		Adapted from Statistics Canada (ESCC 2011). Warning rev1 contains errors: replaced by rev1b in the questionnaire Rev1b in Version 2
Stress and worries over personal finances due to the crisis	emp7	All		From Statistics Canada's Covid survey

Section – Couple relationship

Variable name	Label	Targeted population	Additional rules	Comments
Length of relationship with current partner	cou9 to cou11	People in a couple relationship		
Couple relationship: Dyadic Adjustment Scale	cou1 to cou8	People in a couple relationship		From Spanier, 1976. Selected questions.

Section – Separated parents

Variable name	Label	Targeted population	Additional rules	Comments
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Contacts (of the participant or his child) with the other parent	sep0	Separated parents		
Satisfaction with the amount of time spent with the children, since the lockdown	2-sep	Separated parents	Contacts with the other parent ([sep0]=1)	Statistics Canada (2013). General social survey (ESG) family (2011). https://www.statcan.gc.ca/fra/enquete/menages/4501
Respect of the verbal or written agreement regarding the amount of time spent with children, since the lockdown	1-sep	Separated parents	Contacts with the other parent ([sep0]=1)	Statistics Canada (2013). General social survey (ESG) family (2011). https://www.statcan.gc.ca/fra/enquete/menages/4501
Satisfaction with sharing parental responsibilities with ex-partner, since the lockdown	5-sep	Separated parents	Contacts with the other parent ([sep0]=1)	Saint-Jacques, M.-C., Baude, A., Godbout, É., Robitaille, C., Goubau, D., Pacaut, P., Biland, É., Dubeau, D., Régnier-Loilier, A. et al. (2018). <i>Enquête longitudinale auprès des parents séparés et recomposés du Québec</i> , Université Laval, https://doi.org/10.5683/SP2/SJWLPK .
Since lockdown, when leaving to see the other parent, the children are enthusiastic and happy or sad and troubled	3-sep, 4-sep	Separated parents	Contacts with the other parent ([sep0]=1)	Australian Institute of Family Studies (2020). Growing Up in Australia - The Longitudinal Study of Australian Children (LSAC). https://growingupinaustralia.gov.au/data-and-documentation/accessing-lsac-data
Coparentating scale	SEP (5 questions, 6-sep to 10-sep)	Separated parents	Contacts with the other parent ([sep0]=1)	Feinberg, M. E., Brown, L. D. and Kan, M. L. (2012). A Multi-Domain Self-Report Measure of Coparenting. <i>Parenting Science and Practice</i> , 12(1), 1–21. doi: 10.1080/15295192.2012.638870
Frequency of unpleasant disagreement between the two parents, since the lockdown	11-sep	Separated parents	Contacts with the other parent ([sep0]=1)	Adaptation of Tschann, J. M., Flores, E., Pasch, L. A. and VanOss Marin, B. (1999). Assessing Interparental Conflict: Reports of Parents and Adolescents in European American and Mexican American Families. <i>Journal of Marriage and Family</i> , 61(2), 269–283. doi:10.2307/353747

Occurrence of moments when children witness interactions between the two parents	14-sep	Separated parents and step-parents	Contacts with the other parent ([sep0]=1)	
Since the lockdown, frequency of tense or sarcastic interactions with the other parent witnessed by the children	12-sep	Separated parents and step-parents	Child witness of exchange between parents ([14-sep]=1)	Feinberg, M. E., Brown, L. D. and Kan, M. L. (2012). A Multi-Domain Self-Report Measure of Coparenting. <i>Parenting Science and Practice</i> , 12(1), 1–21. doi: 10.1080/15295192.2012.638870
Since the lockdown, frequency of arguments with the other parent about a child, in front of this child	13-sep	Separated parents and step-parents	Child witness of exchange between parents ([14-sep]=1)	Feinberg, M. E., Brown, L. D. and Kan, M. L. (2012). A Multi-Domain Self-Report Measure of Coparenting. <i>Parenting Science and Practice</i> , 12(1), 1–21. doi: 10.1080/15295192.2012.638870
Number of other partner's children (<18 years old), living with the participant	rec1	Step-parents		Saint-Jacques, M.-C., Baude, A., Godbout, É., Robitaille, C., Goubau, D., Pacaut, P., Biland, É., Dubeau, D., Régnier-Loilier, A. et al. (2018). <i>Enquête longitudinale auprès des parents séparés et recomposés du Québec</i> , Université Laval, https://doi.org/10.5683/SP2/SJWLPK .
Satisfaction with the sharing of parental responsibilities with partner's children, since the lockdown	rec2	Step-parents		Saint-Jacques, M.-C., Baude, A., Godbout, É., Robitaille, C., Goubau, D., Pacaut, P., Biland, É., Dubeau, D., Régnier-Loilier, A. et al. (2018). <i>Enquête longitudinale auprès des parents séparés et recomposés du Québec</i> , Université Laval, https://doi.org/10.5683/SP2/SJWLPK .
Participant's satisfaction with their relationship with their partner's children, since the lockdown	rec3	Step-parents		Saint-Jacques, M.-C., Baude, A., Godbout, É., Robitaille, C., Goubau, D., Pacaut, P., Biland, É., Dubeau, D., Régnier-Loilier, A. et al. (2018). <i>Enquête longitudinale auprès des parents séparés et recomposés du Québec</i> , Université Laval, https://doi.org/10.5683/SP2/SJWLPK .

Section – Children’s health

Variable name	Label	Targeted population	Additional rules	Comments
Parenting Stress Index	ISP (12 questions, isp1 to isp12)	Adults living with children	With their children ([soc8(1)]=true or [soc8(2)]=true)	Abidin, 1995 (interaction subscale in the Parenting Stress Index)
Parental Self-Efficacy Scale	AEP (5 questions, aep1 to aep5)	Adults living with children	With their own children ([soc8(1)]=true or [soc8(2)]=true)	From Dumka, et al. 1996 (5-item version of Parental Self-Efficacy Scale)
Parent-Child Conflict Tactic Scale	AGP (13 questions, agp1 to agp13)	Adults living with children	With their own children ([soc8(1)]=true or [soc8(2)]=true)	Parent-Child Conflict Tactic Scale, Straus et al. 1998
Parenting Scale	PAR (11 questions, par1 to par11)	Adults living with children	With their own children ([soc8(1)]=true or [soc8(2)]=true)	From an ISQ survey (<i>Enquête sur les attitudes parentales</i> , Clément, et al. 2019) based on the Multidimensional Neglectful Behavior Scale and the survey “ <i>Place aux parents</i> ”.
Quality and quantity of the child's sleep	Some1 to som16	Adults living with children	With their own children ([soc8(1)]=true or [soc8(2)]=true)	
Presence of child’s irresistible need to move associated with unpleasant sensations in legs	bou1	Adults living with children	With their own children ([soc8(1)]=true or [soc8(2)]=true)	

Behaviour scale	COM (25 questions, com1 to com25)	Adults living with children	With their own children ([soc8(1)]=true or [soc8(2)]=true)	From Strength and Difficulty Questionnaire by Goodman, 2001
Presence of difficulties in one of these areas (emotions, concentration, behavior, relationships with others) in the child	com26	Adults living with children	With their own children ([soc8(1)]=true or [soc8(2)]=true)	From Strength and Difficulty Questionnaire by Goodman, 2001
Number of months since the onset of these difficulties (difficulties variable com26)	com27	Adults living with children	With their own children ([soc8(1)]=true or [soc8(2)]=true) and Child with difficulties ([com26]=1 or 2 or 3)	From Strength and Difficulty Questionnaire by Goodman, 2001
Measure of disturbance on the child caused by these difficulties (difficulties variable com26)	com28	Adults living with children	With their own children ([soc8(1)]=true or [soc8(2)]=true) and Child with difficulties ([com26]=1 or 2 or 3)	From Strength and Difficulty Questionnaire by Goodman, 2001
Measure of the interference of these difficulties (difficulties variable com26) with the child's daily life, life at home, friendships, learning at school, leisure activities	com29 to com33	Adults living with children	With their own children ([soc8(1)]=true or [soc8(2)]=true) and Child with difficulties ([com26]=1 or 2 or 3)	From Strength and Difficulty Questionnaire by Goodman, 2001
Measure of the burden of these difficulties on the participant or their family	com34	Adults living with children	With their own children ([soc8(1)]=true or [soc8(2)]=true) and Child with difficulties ([com26]=1 or 2 or 3)	From Strength and Difficulty Questionnaire by Goodman, 2001

Section - Foster family

Variable name	Label	Targeted population	Additional rules	Comments
Frequency of face-to-face contacts between the child and their biological parent(s), for the 6 months preceding lockdown	acc1	Foster parents		Self-developed questions
Changes in the frequency of parent-child contacts, since the lockdown	acc2	Foster parents		Self-developed questions
Use of phone or socio-digital media to allow the child to remain in contact with their biological parent(s), since lockdown	acc3, acc3a	Foster parents		Self-developed questions
Perception of a good adaptation of the child to changes made to the contact arrangements	acc4	Foster parents		Self-developed questions
Participant satisfaction regarding the suspension of visitation rights during the lockdown set up by the government	acc5, acc5a	Foster parents		Self-developed questions
Important aspects not addressed that the participant wants to share	acc6	Foster parents		Self-developed questions Qualitative variable

Section – Chronic illnesses management

Variable name	Label	Targeted population	Additional rules	Comments
Regular medication	med1	Chronic physical or mental illness		
Forgetting to take medication in the last two weeks	med2	Chronic physical or mental illness	Regular medication ([med1]=1)	
Forgotten medication more or less frequently since the lockdown	med3	Chronic physical or mental illness	Regular medication ([med1]=1)	
Difficulty getting prescribed medication since the start of lockdown	cons15	Chronic physical or mental illness		
Reasons preventing the participant from obtaining their prescription drugs	cons16	Chronic physical or mental illness	If there is a lack of prescription drugs ([cons15]=2)	
Contact between the participant and their doctor since the lockdown	chro1	Chronic physical or mental illness		
Other than the physician, consultation of other health services or professionals	chro2, chro2a	Chronic physical or mental illness		
Use of resources or tools to manage the disease	chro3, chro3a	Chronic physical or mental illness		Qualitative variable

Elements that helped the participant the most to manage their illness since lockdown	chro4	Chronic physical or mental illness	Qualitative variable
Elements causing concerns regarding their illness and the pandemic	chro5	Chronic physical or mental illness	Qualitative variable

Section - Caregivers

Variable name	Label	Targeted population	Additional rules	Comments
Place where the assisted person lives	pro29	Caregivers		
Caregiver scale - Burden Scale for Family Caregivers	PRO (28 questions, pro1 to pro28)	Caregivers		From Gräsel, et al. 2003
Children ≤ 18 years old with disabilities	proe1	Caregivers		
Number of children with disabilities	proe2	Caregivers	Children ≤ 18 years old with disabilities ([proe1]=1)	
Link between the child and the participant	proe3	Caregivers	Children ≤ 18 years old with disabilities ([proe1]=1)	
Category of the child's disability	proe3b, proe3ba	Caregivers	Children ≤ 18 years old with disabilities ([proe1]=1)	
Child's diagnosis/-es	proe_dx, proe_dxa	Caregivers	Children ≤ 18 years old with disabilities ([proe1]=1)	

Measures of the effect of changes to the organization and operation of services on the support received by the participant in response to their needs	proe4	Caregivers	Children ≤ 18 years old with disabilities ([proe1]=1)
Participant implementation of an educational support routine for the child	proe5	Caregivers	Children ≤ 18 years old with disabilities ([proe1]=1)
Measures of maintaining interpersonal relationships with family and friends by using communication technologies	proe6	Caregivers	Children ≤ 18 years old with disabilities ([proe1]=1)
Measure of the ability to meet the child's needs	proe7	Caregivers	Children ≤ 18 years old with disabilities ([proe1]=1)
Measure of the impact of the suspension of parents associations' activities on families who need support	proe8	Caregivers	Children ≤ 18 years old with disabilities ([proe1]=1)
Measure of the impact of the suspension of weekend respite services on the participant's workload regarding the child and family	proe9	Caregivers	Children ≤ 18 years old with disabilities ([proe1]=1)

Level of stress due to uncertainty regarding the availability of summer camps	proe10	Caregivers	Children ≤ 18 years old with disabilities ([proe1]=1)	Version 1 only
Measure of the response to the child's needs by health and social services network workers despite the changes made in the organization of the services offered	proe11	Caregivers	Children ≤ 18 years old with disabilities ([proe1]=1)	

Section - Participants 14 to 17 year-olds

Variable name	Label	Targeted population	Additional rules	Comments
Participant's place of residence , rehabilitation center or group home	ado1, ado2	Youths		
Participant's 2019 individual annual income	rev2	Youths	Living in a home ([ado1]=1 or [ado2]=1)	
Group Climate Scale	REA (9 questions, rea1 to rea9)	Youths	Living in a home ([ado1]=1 or [ado2]=1)	From Mathys, C., Lanctôt, N. & Touchette, L. (2013)

Section – Quality of the environment

Variable name	Label	Targeted population	Additional rules	Comments
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Type of impairment or significant and persistent disability	inc1	Disabilities		Inc1 version 1 /incb updated in May 2021 in French and only one version in English: has additional answer choices (13).
Legally blind participant	inc3	Disabilities	Vision impairments ([inc1b(1)]=true)	
Legally deaf participant	inc4	Disabilities	Hearing disabilities ([inc1b(2)]=true)	Version 1 only
Participant considering themselves hearing impaired or deaf	inc4b	Disabilities	Hearing disabilities ([inc1b(2)]=true)	Version 2 only
Timing of hearing impairment onset	inc10	Disabilities	Hearing disabilities ([inc1b(2)]=true)	
Presence of patient communication difficulties	inc5, inc5a	Disabilities	Hearing disabilities ([inc1b(2)]=true)	
Presence of difficulties communicating with other people	inc6	Disabilities	Hearing disabilities ([inc1b(2)]=true)	
Participant's impression of having adequate access to information related to government measures	inc7, inc7a	Disabilities	Hearing disabilities ([inc1b(2)]=true)	Valid variable from participant 720
Participant's impression of having access to all the information they need	inc8, inc8a	Disabilities	Hearing disabilities ([inc1b(2)]=true)	Valid variable from participant 720

Use of a walking aid or wheelchair	inc9	Disabilities	Disabilities regarding mobility ([inc1b(3)]=true)	Valid variable from participant 720
Type of residential accommodation (obsolete)	inc2	Disabilities	Adults excluding elderly ([age1]<=64)	Invalid variable left by error at the start of phase 1
The Quality of My Environment Scale (MQE)	MQE (66 questions, mqe1 to mqe78)	Disabilities		Adapted from Fougeryrollas, et al . 2008. 12 questions are missing (34 to 45 the addition was made from participant F2663 or A51 onward). Questions referring to before lockdown in version 1 only .

Section - Life habits since/before the lockdown

Variable name	Label	Targeted population	Additional rules	Comments
Means by which the participant found out about the study	source_etude	Disabilities		
Diagnosis/-es applicable to the participant	dx_incapacit	Disabilities		
Presence of protective supervision (such as the <i>Curateur public du Québec</i>)	regime_protect	Disabilities		
Level of increase in support provided to the participant due to their limitations or disabilities	q_ind_incap1	Disabilities		
The measures put in place to fight the pandemic	q_ind_incap2	Disabilities		

consider the situation of people with disabilities		
Availability of necessary human, physical and financial support	q_ind_incap3	Disabilities
Use of social media as a source of information about the pandemic	q_ind_incap4	Disabilities
Accessibility of means of communication used by public authorities	q_ind_incap5	Disabilities
Comprehension and accessibility of the information communicated by public authorities	q_ind_incap6	Disabilities
The information communicated by the public authorities concerns the participant	q_ind_incap7	Disabilities
The needs of people with disabilities have been met by public authorities	q_ind_incap8	Disabilities
Level of access to services and support needed	q_ind_incap9	Disabilities
Level of disturbance of activities of daily living caused by the sanitary	q_ind_incap10	Disabilities

Use of communication technology to maintain interpersonal relationships	q_ind_incap11	Disabilities	
Increased social isolation due to changes in the services received	q_ind_incap12	Disabilities	
Measure of the impact of cancelled socio-professional and community activities on the participant's daily life	q_ind_incap13	Disabilities	
Measure of the importance of organizations for the collective defense of the rights of people with disabilities in maintaining services and access to information	q_ind_incap14	Disabilities	
Adequate support from family and loved ones	q_ind_incap15	Disabilities	
Gender differences in people with disabilities regarding the impact of implementing measures to fight the pandemic	q_ind_incap16	Disabilities	
Lifestyle habits since the start of lockdown	mhave_XXXX# (items 1 to 32 : 5 questions each)	Disabilities	Adapted from Fougeyrollas and Noreau 2014

Lifestyle habits before the start of lockdown	mhave_XXXX#_pre (items 1 to 32 : 5 questions each)	Disabilities	Adapted from Fougeyrollas and Noreau 2014 Version 1 only
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Section – Health and social workers

Variable name	Label	Targeted population	Additional rules	Comments
Participant's profession in the health network	emp8	RSSS actors		Up to participant 345, single choice question. From F346 onward, multiple choice question
Work sector	emp9	RSSS actors	Social worker ([emp8(2)]=true)	
Title of the position held	emp10	RSSS actors		
Work scale (Questions for social workers)	TRA (8 questions, tra1 to tra8)	RSSS actors		In-house questions developed by the CRUJeF.
Work-related beliefs	CRO (12 questions, cro1 to cro6 and cro11 to cro16)	RSSS actors		
Work-related changes	CHAN (10 questions, chan1 to chan10)	RSSS actors		
Measures of professional burnout - From the Maslach Burnout Inventory	fat1 and fat2	RSSS actors		From Maslach, et al. 1996 (selected questions)
Motivation at work scale	mot1 to mot6	RSSS actors		From Snyder, 1996 : valid variable from participant F271 onward

Participant's concern about caring for patients diagnosed with or likely to have COVID-19	avis1	RSSS actors	Qualitative variable
Relevant training for the participant in the context of the pandemic	avis2	RSSS actors	Qualitative variable
Important element that may have improved the well-being of the participant	avis3	RSSS actors	Qualitative variable
Examples of approaches, changes in work organization, interventions, favorable policies or any other positive element in the participant's field of work	avis3b	RSSS actors	Qualitative variable

Section - Final questions

Variable name	Label	Targeted population	Additional rules	Comments
Sharing a testimony or an experience lived by the participant since lockdown	avis4	All		Qualitative variable
Topics not covered, but considered important by the participant	avis5	All		Qualitative variable
Person having answered the questions	lit1	All		Qualitative variable

4. MENTAL HEALTH FOLLOW-UPS QUESTIONNAIRE

4.1 Structure of the questionnaire

SECTION	POPULATION	PAGE
CORE		
Eligibility and sociodemographic status	All	51
Employment situation	All	51
Health	All	52
Well-being	All	52
Emotional health	All	52
Social support	All	53
COVID-19 exposure	All	53
Physical and leisure activities, consumption profiles	All	54
Final questions	All	56

4.2 Definition of populations (sub-cohorts)

Population	Description	Identification variables
All (all populations below are subpopulations of this group)	Population living in Quebec	[reg1] <> '100'
Adults	18 years old and over	age1 > 17
People in a couple relationship	People in a couple relationship, living or not with their partner	([soc5] = 2 OR [soc5] = 1) and [age1] > 17

4.3 Indicators and populations (commented)

SECTION – MAVIPAN - Eligibility and sociodemographic status

Variable name	Label	Targeted population	Additional rules	Comments
Region of residence	reg1	All		
Age of participant	age1	All		
Relationship status	soc5	Adults		
Marital status of the participant	soc4	Adults		Statistics Canada measure
Degree of happiness in the relationship	cou1	Adults in a couple relationship		From the Dyadic Adjustment Scale (Spanier, 1976)

SECTION - Employment situation

Variable name	Label	Targeted population	Additional rules	Comments
Main occupation	emp3	All		Emp3a from Follow-up 2 (October 2020) . Slight modification to choice 4 from Follow-up 3 (February 2021) .
Loss of job or main source of income in the near future	emp4	All	If paid job ([emp3]=1 or 2 or 3)	
Frequency of feeling exhausted from work in the past month	fat1b	Adults	If paid job ([emp3]=1 or 2 or 3)	From Maslach Burnout Inventory (Maslach, et al. 1996). Response scale changed in Follow-ups vs Baseline to be applicable to the last month.
Current workplace, since last week	emp6	Adults	If paid job ([emp3]=1 or 2 or 3)	

**Back to school and daycare for children
≤ 12 years old** soc11 Adults

SECTION – Health

Variable name	Label	Targeted population	Additional rules	Comments
Perception of physical health	asan4	All		
Perception of change in physical health compared to before lockdown	isan1	All		Follow-up 1 (June 2020) only
Perception of mental health	asan5	All		
Perception of change in mental health, compared to before lockdown	isan2	All		Follow-up 1 (June 2020) only

SECTION - Well-being

Variable name	Label	Targeted population	Additional rules	Comments
Participant's feelings about their own life	sat1	All		
Participant's feelings about their own life compared to before lockdown	sat3	All		Follow-up 1 (June 2020) only
Warwick-Edinburgh Well-being Scale	WEG (7 questions, weg1, weg2, weg3, weg6, weg7, weg9, weg11)	All		See Tennant, et al. 2007. The short version of the scale must be used, because an error was made for the long version (one missing item) preventing its analysis

SECTION - Emotional health

Variable name	Label	Targeted population	Additional rules	Comments
Number of hours of sleep	som10/som10_deroule	All		Som10 was hidden from Follow-up 2 (October 2020) and on, replaced

			with som10_deroule (drop-down list) to avoid cleanup issues.
Insomnia scale	som_etiquette (som1 to som7)	All	From Morin, 1993
Depression Anxiety Stress Scale	DASS (21 questions, dass1 to dass21)	All	From Lovibond and Lovibond, 1995
Hostility scale	HOS (6 questions, hos1 to hos6)	All	From Derogatis, 1994

SECTION - Social support

Variable name	Label	Targeted population	Additional rules	Comments
Loneliness scale	SOL (4 questions, sol1 to sol4)	All		Sol1-2-3 are from Hugues, et al. 2004
Frequency of social interactions with family or friends who do not share a dwelling with the participant, during the last month	ssoc12	All		
Perceptions of the frequency of these interactions	ssoc13	All		

SECTION - COVID-19 exposure

Variable name	Label	Targeted population	Additional rules	Comments
COVID-19 diagnosis in participant and types of symptoms affecting them	exp4	All		Exp4_date from Follow-up 2 (October 2020)
Hospitalization of the participant due to COVID-19	exp5	All	If severe or moderate symptoms ([exp4]=1 or 2)	

Level of concern about a return to lockdown	exp8	All	
Level of concern for own health	exp9	All	
Level of concern for the health of family and loved ones	exp10	All	
Level of concern for work-life balance	exp11	All	
Level of concern about own employment situation	exp12	All	
Level of concern about going to public places	exp13	All	
Vaccination against COVID-19	exp14 (exp_14 for English participants)	All	Only as of Follow-up 3 (February 2021)
Measure of stress and worry over personal finances due to the crisis	emp7	All	
Long COVID Diagnosis	exp15	All	Only as of Follow-up 5 (February 2022)

SECTION - Physical and leisure activities, consumption profiles

Variable name	Label	Targeted population	Additional rules	Comments
Leisure time in front of a screen, per day, in the past month	Act1b/act1b_deroule	All		For the French version: as of Follow-up 2 (October 2020) , act1b has been hidden and replaced by act1b_deroule (drop-down list type of variable).

			For the English version: in Follow-up 2 (October 2020) , the act1b variable was created directly in drop-down list format, but the “_deroule” suffix was forgotten. The same variable therefore has a different name in the French (act1b_deroule) and English (act1b) versions
Time spent walking, per day, in the past month	Act4b/act4b_deroule	All	Same as act1b
Time spent in leisure cardiorespiratory-type physical activities, per week, in the past month	Act7b/act7b_deroule	All	Same as act1b
Time spent in high intensity leisure cardiorespiratory-type physical activities, per week, in the past month	Act10b/act10b_deroule	All	Same as act1b
Types of physical activity done at home in the past month	act15b	All	Beware of the inconsistency between the baseline questionnaire and the follow-ups: act15b in the follow-ups corresponds to act14_0_bis in the Baseline 2 questionnaire and to act15 in baseline 1
Consumption scale	CONS (15 questions, cons1 to cons15)	All	Follow-up 1 (June 2020) only

Assessment of alcohol consumption during lockdown, compared to before lockdown	alcohol_conf	All	Follow-up 1 (June 2020) only
New consumption scale	Cons7_b to _14, aliment1, cafe1, alcohol (3), tabac (2), vapotage (2) drogue1		Follow-up 2 (October 2020) - retention of certain questions, modification of certain answer options and new questions for alcohol, tobacco and vaping (see questionnaire)
Time spent investigating the COVID-19 crisis, per day	inf1	All	

SECTION - Final questions

Variable name	Label	Targeted population	Additional rules	Comments
Participant sharing a testimonial or a lived experience having occurred since the start of the pandemic or any other comment	avis6	All		

5. QUESTIONNAIRE AD HOC 1 DECEMBER 2020

5.1 Structure of the questionnaire

SECTION	POPULATION	PAGE
CORE		
Eligibility and sociodemographic status	All	60
Employment et education	All	61
Mental health and resilience	All	64
Rural areas	All	65
SUB-COHORTS		
Family-Work balance	Adults	63
Education-Work-Life Concerns	Underage and students	63
Stress parental	Adults living with children, including step-parents	65
Final questions	All	65

5.2 Definition of populations (sub-cohorts)

Population	Description	Identification variables
All (all populations below are subpopulations of this group)	Population living in Quebec	[reg1] <> '100'
Adults	18 years old and over	[age1] ≥18
Minors	Under 18 years old	[age1] <18

Students	People studying in Fall 2020	[edu2_ah1] = 01 OR [edu2_ah1] = 02 OR [edu2_ah1] = 03 OR [edu2_ah1] = 04
Update	Participants who answered the baseline questionnaire more than a month before sending the Ad Hoc	FR: [record_id] <= 2751 EN: no condition
Groups³ per date	See description below (Section 5.3)	
RSSS actors	Actors working in the health and social services network	emp1_ah1 =1
Employed	Employed people	emp3_ah1 = 1, 2 or 3
Employed at baseline	People employed when they answered the baseline questionnaire	emp3_baseline = 1, 2 or 3
Adults living with children	Adults living with one or more children under 18 years old (being their parent or not)	([soc6_ah1] = 1) and [age1] >17

5.3 Groups of participants according to the date on which they answered the baseline questionnaire

Group	Dates	Participant numbers in the French project	Participant numbers in the English project
Group 1 (g1)	April 29 to May 10	1 to 985 and 987 to 1016	None
Group 2 (g2)	May 11 to May 31	986 and 1017 to 1798	1 to 7
Group 3 (g3)	June	1799 to 2753	8 to 48

³ The groups shown above are different from the arms described earlier in the text. Groups correspond to subsets of the sample that responded to the baseline questionnaire at a specific point in time. We adapted the wording of the questions according to these groups in the Ad Hoc questionnaire. For example, we customized the reference month for questions about the terms and conditions of employment when participants answered the baseline questionnaire, and this, based on the month in which participants responded to this questionnaire. A participant who answered the baseline questionnaire in June thus saw the following formulation of the question: "In June, in which activity sector was your main job?"

Group 4 (g4)	July	2574 to 2658 and 2660 to 2668	49 and 50
Group 5 (g5)	August	2659 and 2669 to 2702	51 to 60
Group 6 (g6)	September	2703 to 2713	61
Group 7 (g7)	October	2714 to 2740	62
Group 8 (g8)	November	2741 to 2759	None

5.4 Indicators and populations (commented)

Section - MAVIPAN – Eligibility

Variable name	Label	Targeted population	Additional rules	Comments
Region of residence	reg1	All		
Age of participant	age1	All		

Section – Sociodemographic status

Variable name	Label	Targeted population	Additional rules	Comments
Number of rooms in dwelling	log1_ah1	Update		
Number of people living in dwelling	log2_ah1	Update		
Type of dwelling	log5_ah1	Update		
First three characters of postal code	zip1_ah1	Update		
Relationship status	soc5_ah1	Update and Adults		
Presence of minor children in the housing	soc6_ah1	Adults		
Age of minor children	soc7_ah1 (soc71_ah1 to soc76_ah1)	Adults living with children		
Family situation	soc8_ah1	Adults living with children		

Single parent family	soc10_ah1	Adults living with children
Participant's marital status	soc4_ah1	Update and Adults
Registration in an educational establishment in the Fall	edu2_ah1	All

SECTION - Employment and education

Variable name	Label	Targeted population	Additional rules	Comments
Employment status	emp3_ah1	All		
Employment status at Follow-up 2	emp3_retro_ah1	All		
Current workplace, since last week	emp6_ah1	Adults	If paid job ([emp3]=1 or 2 or 3)	
Actor in the health and social services network	emp1_ah1	All		
Participant's profession in the health and social services network	emp8_ah1	RSSS actors		
Direct customer care or services	emp10_ah1	RSSS actors		
Work sector	emp9_ah1	RSSS actors		
Work area	emp12_ah1	Employed and excluding RSSS actors		Quebec entrepreneurial index (adapted from Statistics Canada)
Field of employment when baseline questionnaire completed	emp12_retro_ah1	Employed at baseline and	Question formulated by group (based on	

		excluding RSSS actors	completion date of baseline questionnaire)
Sedentarity of employment	emp13_ah1	Employed	
Sedentarity of employment when baseline questionnaire completed	emp13_retro_ah1	Employed at baseline	Question formulated by group (based on completion date of baseline questionnaire)
Work schedule	emp14_ah1	Employed	
Work schedule when baseline questionnaire completed	emp14_retro_ah1	Employed at baseline	Question formulated by group (based on completion date of baseline questionnaire)
24/7 on-call job	emp15_ah1	Employed	
24/7 on-call job when baseline questionnaire completed	emp15_retro_ah1	Employed at baseline	Question formulated by group (based on completion date of baseline questionnaire)
Atypical working hours	emp16_ah1	Employed	
Atypical working hours when baseline questionnaire completed	emp16_retro_ah1	Employed at baseline	Group 1 only
Additional workload	emp17_ah1	Employed	
Additional workload when completed baseline questionnaire	emp17_retro_ah1	Employed at baseline	Group 1 only

Internet needs	int1_ah1	All	
Internet connection access and reason if answers no	int2_ah1 and int2_b_ah1	All	Depending on int1
Internet satisfaction and reason if dissatisfied	int3_ah1 and int3_b_ah1	All	Depending on int1 and int2

SECTION - Family-Work balance

Variable name	Label	Targeted population	Additional rules	Comments
Childcare	trafam1_ah1	Adults living with children		Adapted from Tremblay and Roy (2015)
Childcare during first lockdown	trafam1_retro_ah1	Adults living with children	Group 1	Adapted from Tremblay and Roy (2015)
Sharing of household tasks	trafam2_ah1	Adults		Adapted from Tremblay and Roy (2015)
Sharing of household tasks during first lockdown	trafam2_retro_ah1	Adults	Group 1	Adapted from Tremblay and Roy (2015)
Unpaid hours spent on housework, caring for children and people in need of care	trafam3_ah1, trafam4_ah1 and trafam5_ah1	Adults		Statistics Canada (2015). General social survey on the use of time.

SECTION - Education-Work-Life Concerns

Variable name	Label	Targeted population	Additional rules	Comments
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Concerns of young people for education and employment	preocc_etu1_ah1 to preocc_etu11_ah1	Students	A) Preocc_etu1_ah1 and preocc_etu2_ah1: From Statistics Canada (2020) B) Preocc_etu4_ah1 and preocc_etu5_ah1: From Longitudinal study of the development of children in Quebec (Quebec Institute of Statistics) C) preocc_etu6_ah1 and preocc_etu11_ah1: From Gaudreault, Gaudreault and Blackburn-Verreault (2013)
Time spent studying per day	temps_etu_ah1	Students	

SECTION - Mental health and resilience

Variable name	Label	Targeted population	Additional rules	Comments
Difficulties associated with behaviours and feelings with others, studies, love life, work and leisure	sant_ment1_ah1 to sant_ment6_ah1	Students for sant_ment2_ah1		From Longitudinal study of the development of children in Quebec (Quebec Institute of Statistics)
Relationships with parents	relparent1_ah1 and relparent2_ah2	Minors		From Longitudinal study of the development of children in Quebec (Quebec Institute of Statistics)
Parenting Stress Index	ISP_ah1 (12 questions, isp1_ah1 to isp12_ah1)	Adults living with children	With their own children ([soc8(1)]=true or [soc8(2)]=true)	Abidin (1995) (interaction subscale in the Parenting Stress Index)
Resilience scale (CD-RISC-10)	res1_ah1 to res10_ah1	All		Çonnor and Davidson (2003)

SECTION – Stress parental

Parenting Stress Index	ISP_ah1 (12 questions, isp1_ah1 to isp12_ah1)	Adults living with children	With their own children ([soc8(1)]=true or [soc8(2)]=true)	Abidin (1995) (interaction subscale in the Parenting Stress Index)
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SECTION – Rural areas

Variable name	Label	Targeted population	Additional rules	Comments
Metropolitan area	rural1_ah1	All		
Perceptions regarding governmental decisions	rural2_ah1 to rural6_ah1	All		

SECTION - Final questions

Variable name	Label	Targeted population	Additional rules	Comments
Participant sharing a testimonial or a lived experience since lockdown	avis4	All		Qualitative variable
Topics not covered, but important to the participant	avis5	All		Qualitative variable
Individual having responded to questions	lit1	All		Qualitative variable

6. AD HOC 2 (MAY 2021) and AD HOC 3 (MAY 2022) QUESTIONNAIRES

6.1 Questionnaire structure

SECTION	POPULATION	PAGE
CORE		
Eligibility and sociodemographic status	All	69
Employment and Education	All	70
Coping strategies and resilience	All	75
Social support	All	76
SUB-COHORTS		
Education-Work-Life Concerns	Underage and students	71
Health status and history section	All and Participants with a chronic illness or a mental health disorder	72
Couple relationship	Participants in a relationship	76
Participants 14-17 years old (Ad Hoc 2 (May 2021) only)	Youths living in a group home or a rehabilitation center	77
Separated parents	Separated parents	77
Children's health	Adults living with children, including step-parents	80
Foster Families (Ad Hoc 2 (May 2021) only)	Foster families	83
Caregivers	Caregivers	84
Quality of the environment	Individuals with disabilities	86
Life habits	Individuals with disabilities	87
Health and social services workers	Health and social services workers	90
Final questions	All	91

6.2 Population définition (sub-cohorts)

Population	Description	Identification variables
All (all populations below are sub-cohorts of this group)	Populations living in Québec	[reg1] <> '100'
Adults	18 years old and over	[age1] ≥18
Minors	Under 18 years old	[age1] <18
Students	People attending school in Fall 2020	[edu2_ah2] = 01 OR [edu2_ah2] = 02 OR [edu2_ah2] = 03 OR [edu2_ah2] = 04
Employed	People who are employed	emp3_ah2 = 1, 2 ou 3
Presence of chronic disease	Populations with one or many chronic diseases	([asan1_ah2] ≤ 11)
Presence of mental illness	Populations with a mental health disorder	([asan8_ah2] = 1)
Disabilities	People with one or many disabilities	([asan2_ah2] = 1 or [asan3_ah2 (10)] = true)
Population in a couple relationship	People in a couple relationship, living or not with their partner	([soc5_ah2] = 2 OR [soc5_ah2] = 1) and [age1] > 17
Separated parents	People with children but no longer in a couple relationship with the other parent	[soc8_ah2 (2)] = true and [age1] > 17
Step-parents	People living with the children from their partner's previous union	[soc8_ah2 (3)] = true and [age1] > 17
Adults living with children	Adults living with one or more children under 18 years old (being their parent or not)	([soc6_ah2] = 1) and [age1] > 17
Foster parents	Adults caring for foster children	([soc8_ah2 (4)] = true) and [age1] > 17
Caregivers	Adults in a caregiving role	[cha1_ah2] = 1 and [age1] > 17

RSSS actors	Actors working in the health and social services network	[age1] > 17 and [emp1_ah2] = 1 and (([emp3_ah2] = 1 or [emp3_ah2] = 2 or [emp3_ah2] = 3)
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6.3 Population indicators (commented)

Section – MAVIPAN - Eligibility

Variable name	Label	Targeted population	Additional rules	Comments
Region of residence	reg1	All		
Age of participant	age1	All		
Romantic situation	soc5_ah2	Adults		
Marital situation	soc4_ah2	Adults		

Section - Sociodémographic status

Variable name	Label	Targeted population	Additional rules	Comments
Gender	sex1_ah2	All		
Number of rooms in dwelling	log1_ah2	All		
Number of individuals living in dwelling	log2_ah2	All		
Pet living in dwelling	log4_ah2	All		
Type of dwelling	log5_ah2	All		
First three characters of postal code	zip1_ah2	All		
Presence of minor(s) and children in dwelling	soc6_ah2	Adults		

Age of minor children	soc7_ah2 (soc71_ah2 to soc76_ah2)	Adults living with children	
Family situation	soc8_ah2	Adults living with children	
Single-parent family	soc10_ah2	Adults living with children	
Participant's matrimonial status	soc4_ah2	Adults	
Status in Canada	soc1_ah2	All	Adapted from Statistics Canada 2016
Annual family income for 2020	rev1b_ah2	Adults	Adapted from Statistics Canada (CCHS 2011).
Individuals with special health needs under participant's care (caregiver)	cha1_ah2	Adults	
Number of children (<18 years old) with these special health needs	cha4_ah2	Caregivers	
Number of adults (18-64 years old) with these special health needs	cha5_ah2	Caregivers	
Number of adults (≥65 years old) with these special health needs	cha6_ah2	Caregivers	

SECTION - Employment – education

Variable name	Label	Targeted population	Additional rules	Comments
Highest education level	edu1_ah2	All		Adapted from Statistics Canada (CCHS 2011)

Registration at educational establishment in Fall	edu2_ah2	All		
Employment status	emp3_ah2	All		
Employed by an essential service	emp5_ah2	All	If remunerated employment ([emp3_ah2]=1 or 2 or 3)	According to the 2021 list of the Government of Quebec
Employment field	emp12_ah2	Employed and excluding RSSS actors		Quebec Entrepreneurship Index (and adapted from Statistics Canada)
Actual job location, since last week	emp6_ah2	Adults	If remunerated employment ([emp3]=1 or 2 or 3)	
Sedentarity of job	emp13_ah2	Employed		
Work schedule	emp14_ah2	Employed		
On-call job 24h/24h	emp15_ah2	Employed		
Atypical work schedule	emp16_ah2	Employed		
Additional workload	emp17_ah2	Employed		

SECTION - Education-Work-Life Concerns

Variable name	Label	Targeted population	Additional rules	Comments
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Students' concerns regarding school and job	preocc_etu1_ah2 to preocc_etu11_ah2	Students	<p>A) Preocc_etu1_ah1 and preocc_etu2_ah1: From Statistics Canada (2020)</p> <p>B) Preocc_etu4_ah1 and preocc_etu5_ah1: From the <i>Étude longitudinale du développement des enfants du Québec (Institut de la statistique du Québec)</i></p> <p>C) preocc_etu6_ah1 to preocc_etu11_ah1: From Gaudreault, Gaudreault et Blackburn-Verreault (2013)</p>
Time studying per day	temps_etu_ah2	Students	

SECTION - Health status and history section

Variable name	Label	Targeted population	Additional rules	Comments
Presence of persistent and significant deficiencies or disabilities	asan2_ah2	All		
Participant's types of chronic diseases	asan1_ah2	All		
Medical follow-up for chronic disease	asan10_ah2	All	Presence of a chronic disease ([asan1_ah2]≤11)	
Worry of consulting a doctor or being in a clinical environment or other service environment	exp2_ah2	All		
Presence of a mental health problem	asan8_ah2	All		

Participant's type of mental health problem	asan3_ah2	All	Presence of a mental health problem ([asan8_ah2]=1)
Diagnosis by a doctor	asan6_ah2	All	Presence of a mental health problem ([asan8_ah2]=1)
Medical follow-up for a mental health problem	asan9_ah2		Presence of a mental health problem ([asan8_ah2]=1)
Contact between the participant and their doctor	chro1_ah2	Physical or mental chronic disease	
Consultation of services or health professionals other than their doctor	chro2_ah2	Physical or mental chronic disease	
Use of resources or tools to manage a disease	chro3_ah2	Physical or mental chronic disease	Qualitative variable
Forgotten medication, in the last two weeks	med2_ah2	Physical or mental chronic disease	Regular medication ([med1_ah2]=1)
Forgetting more or less frequently since lockdown	med3_ah2	Physical or mental chronic disease	Regular medication ([med1_ah2]=1)
Getting prescribed medication since the start of lockdown	cons15_ah2	Physical or mental chronic disease	
Reasons preventing the participant from getting their prescribed medication	cons16_ah2	Physical or mental chronic disease	If missing prescribed medication ([cons15_ah2]=2)
Delay of medical procedure	soin1_ah2	All	

Wait after delay of medical procedure	soin1a_ah2	All	soin1_ah2=1	
Medical needs met before the pandemic	soin2_ah2	All		
Medical needs met since the pandemic	soin3_ah2	All		
Reasons for unmet needs	soin4_ah2	All	Soin3_ah2 = 3 or 4	Qualitative variable
Professional mental health consultation	soin5_ah2	All		
1st professional mental health consultation	soin6_ah2	All	Has consulted a professional ([soin5_ah2] = 01, 02, 03 ou 04)	
Other mental health recourse resource	soin7_ah2	All		
Type of resource	soin8_ah2	All		Qualitative variable
Has received the needed mental health services before the pandemic	soin9_ah2	All		
Has received the needed mental health services since the pandemic	soin10_ah2	All		
Reasons for unmet needs	soin11_ah2	All		Qualitative variable
Element that most helps the participant manage their disease	chro4_ah2	Physical or mental chronic disease		Qualitative variable
Elements causing concerns for the participant regarding their disease and the pandemic	chro5_ah2	Physical or mental chronic disease		Qualitative variable

Participant height	ant1 ah2	All	
Participant weight	ant2 ah2	All	
Pant or jeans size	ant4 ah2 (men) and ant5 ah2 (women)	All	
Pregnancy in female participant	fem1 ah2	All	Women ([[sex1]=1])
If pregnant, number of weeks of gestation	fem2 ah2	All	Pregnant women ([[fem1]=1])

SECTION - Coping strategies and resilience

Variable name	Label	Targeted population	Additional rules	Comments
Adaptation strategies: Brief Coping Scale	COP (16 questions, cop1_ah2 to cop16_ah2)	All		Adapted from Carver, et al. 2018 (Selected questions)
Participant's feeling regarding their life, one year projection	sat2_ah2	All		Adapted from Statistics Canada (CCHS 2011)
Resilience scale (CD-RISC-10)	res1_ah2 to res10_ah2	All		Çonnor et Davidson (2003)
Post-traumatic growth inventory scale	PTGI (10 questions ptgi1_ah2 to ptgi10_ah2)	All		Cann, et al (2010) and Cadel, et al (2015) for the French version

Evaluation of pandemic impacts	bilan1_ah2	All	
Evaluation of positive impacts of pandemic	bilan2_ah2	All	
Evaluation of negative impacts of pandemic	bilan3_ah2	All	
Ambivalence regarding returning to normal	bilan4_ah2	All	
Positive aspects regarding returning to normal	bilan5_ah2	All	Questionnaire Ad Hoc 2 (May 2021) only
Changes brought about by the pandemic	Bilan6_ah3	All	Questionnaire Ad Hoc 3 only

SECTION – Social support

Variable name	Label	Targeted population	Additional rules	Comments
Social Provision Scale	SSOC (10 questions, ssoc1_ah2 to ssoc10_ah2)	All		From Caron, 2013
Presence of a loved one in a CHSLD or private seniors' residence	exp1_ah2	All		

SECTION – Couple relationships

Time in a relationship with current partner	cou9_ah2 to cou11_ah2	Population in a couple relationship		
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Couple relationship: Dyadic Adjustment Scale	cou1_ah2 to cou8_ah2	Population in a couple relationship	From Spanier, 1976. (selected questions)
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SECTION – Participants 14- to 17 years old

Variable name	Label	Targeted population	Additional rules	Comments
Place where the participant lives, in a rehabilitation center, in a group home	ado1_ah2, ado2_ah2	Minors		Questionnaire Ad Hoc 2 (May 2021) only Not in the English version
Participant's individual annual income 2019	rev2_ah2	Minors	Living group home ([ado1]=1 ou [ado2]=1)	Questionnaire Ad Hoc 2 (May 2021) only Not in the English version
Group climate scale	REA (9 questions, rea1_ah2 to rea9_ah2)	Minors	Living a group home ([ado1]=1 ou [ado2]=1)	Questionnaire Ad Hoc 2 (May 2021) only Not in the English version From Mathys, C., Lanctôt, N. & Touchette, L. (2013)

SECTION – Separated parents

Variable name	Label	Targeted population	Additional rules	Comments
In contact (participant or their child) with the other parent	sep0	Separated parents		

Satisfaction with the quantity of time spent with the children	sep2	Separated parents	Contacts with the other parent ([sep0]=1)	Statistics Canada (2013). General Social Survey (GSS) Family (2011). https://www.statcan.gc.ca/fra/enquete/menages/4501
Respect of the verbal or written agreement regarding the quantity of time spent with the children	Sep1	Separated parents	Contacts with the other parent ([sep0]=1)	Statistics Canada (2013). General Social Survey (GSS) Family (2011). https://www.statcan.gc.ca/fra/enquete/menages/4501
Satisfaction with the splitting of parental responsibilities with the ex-partner	Sep5	Separated parents	Contacts with the other parent ([sep0]=1)	Saint-Jacques, M.-C., Baude, A., Godbout, É., Robitaille, C., Goubau, D., Pacaut, P., Biland, É., Dubeau, D., Régnier-Loilier, A. et collaborateurs. (2018). <i>Enquête longitudinale auprès des parents séparés et recomposés du Québec</i> , Université Laval, https://doi.org/10.5683/SP2/SJWLPK .
Children are enthusiastic and happy or sad and disturbed when leaving to see the other parent	Sep3, sep4	Separated parents	Contacts with the other parent ([sep0]=1)	Australian Institute of Family Studies (2020). Growing Up in Australia - The Longitudinal Study of Australian Children (LSAC). https://growingupinaustralia.gov.au/data-and-documentation/accessing-lsac-data
Separation scale	SEP (5 questions, 6-sep to 10-sep)	Separated parents	Contacts with the other parent ([sep0]=1)	Feinberg, M. E., Brown, L. D. et Kan, M. L. (2012). A Multi-Domain Self-Report Measure of Coparenting. <i>Parenting Science and Practice</i> , 12(1), 1–21. doi: 10.1080/15295192.2012.638870

Frequency of unpleasant disagreements between the two parents	11-sep	Separated parents	Contacts with the other parent ([sep0]=1)	Adapted from Tschann, J. M., Flores, E., Pasch, L. A. et VanOss Marin, B. (1999). Assessing Interparental Conflict: Reports of Parents and Adolescents in EuropeanAmerican and Mexican American Families. <i>Journal of Marriage and Family</i> , 61(2),269-283. doi:10.2307/353747
Occurrence of moments where the children witness interactions between the two parents	14-sep	Separated parents and step-parents	Contacts with the other parent ([sep0]=1)	
Frequency of tense or sarcastic interactions with the other parent witnessed by the children	12-sep	Separated parents and step-parents	Child witness of interaction between parents ([14-sep]=1)	Feinberg, M. E., Brown, L. D. et Kan, M. L. (2012). A Multi-Domain Self-Report Measure of Coparenting. <i>Parenting Science and Practice</i> , 12(1), 1–21. doi: 10.1080/15295192.2012.638870
Frequency of arguments with the other parent about a child, in front of said child	13-sep	Separated parents and step-parents	Child witness of interaction between parents ([14-sep]=1)	Feinberg, M. E., Brown, L. D. et Kan, M. L. (2012). A Multi-Domain Self-Report Measure of Coparenting. <i>Parenting Science and Practice</i> , 12(1), 1–21. doi: 10.1080/15295192.2012.638870
Number of the other partner's children (<18 years old), from a previous relationship living with the participant	rec1	Step-parents		Saint-Jacques, M.-C., Baude, A., Godbout, É., Robitaille, C., Goubau, D., Pacaut, P., Biland, É., Dubeau, D., Régnier-Loilier, A. et collaborateurs. (2018). <i>Enquête longitudinale auprès des parents séparés et recomposés du Québec</i> , Université Laval, https://doi.org/10.5683/SP2/SJWLPK .

Satisfaction with the sharing of parental responsibilities regarding the partner's children	rec2	Step-parents	Saint-Jacques, M.-C., Baude, A., Godbout, É., Robitaille, C., Goubau, D., Pacaut, P., Biland, É., Dubeau, D., Régnier-Loilier, A. et collaborateurs. (2018). <i>Enquête longitudinale auprès des parents séparés et recomposés du Québec</i> , Université Laval, https://doi.org/10.5683/SP2/SJWLPK .
Satisfaction with the participant's relationship with their partner's children	rec3	Step-parents	Saint-Jacques, M.-C., Baude, A., Godbout, É., Robitaille, C., Goubau, D., Pacaut, P., Biland, É., Dubeau, D., Régnier-Loilier, A. et collaborateurs. (2018). <i>Enquête longitudinale auprès des parents séparés et recomposés du Québec</i> , Université Laval, https://doi.org/10.5683/SP2/SJWLPK .

SECTION – Children's health

Name of variable	Label	Targeted population	Additional rules	Comments
Parental Stress Index	ISP (12 questions, isp1 to isp12)	Adults living with children	With their own children ([soc8_ah2(1)]=true or [soc8_ah2(2)]=true)	Abidin, 1995 (interaction sub-scale in the Parenting Stress Index)
Parental Self-Efficacy Scale	AEP (5 questions, aep1 to aep5)	Adults living with children	With their own children ([soc8_ah2(1)]=true or [soc8_ah2(2)]=true)	From Dumka, et al 1996 (5 item version of Parental Self-Efficacy Scale)

Minor physical and psychological aggression scale	AGP (13 questions, agp1 to agp13)	Adults living with children	With their own children ([soc8_ah2(1)]=true or [soc8_ah2(2)]=true	Clément, et al. 2018 (translation of the Parent-Child Conflict Tactic Scale from Straus, et al. 1998)
Parenthood scale	PAR (11 questions, par1 to par11)	Adults living with children	Living with their own children ([soc8_ah2(1)]=true or [soc8_ah2(2)]=true	From an ISQ survey (<i>Enquête sur les attitudes parentales</i> , Clément, et al 2019) which is based on the Multidimensional Neglectful Behavior Scale et and the “Place aux parents” survey.
Quality and quantity of child’s sleep	Some1 to som16	Adults living with children	Living with their own children ([soc8_ah2(1)]=true or [soc8_ah2(2)]=true	
Presence of child’s irresistible need to move associated with unpleasant sensations in the legs	bou1	Adults living with children	Living with their own children ([soc8_ah2(1)]=true or [soc8_ah2(2)]=true	
Behaviour scale	COM (25 questions, com1 à com25)	Adults living with children	Living with their own children ([soc8_ah2(1)]=true or [soc8_ah2(2)]=true	From the Strength and Difficulty Questionnaire de Goodman, 2001
Child with difficulties in one of these domains (emotions, concentration, behaviour, relationships with others)	com26	Adults living with children	Living with their own children ([soc8_ah2(1)]=true	From the Strength and Difficulty Questionnaire de Goodman, 2001

			or [soc8_ah2 (2)]=true	
Number of months since the appearance of these difficulties (difficulties variable com26)	com27	Adults living with children	With their own children ([soc8(1)]=true or [soc8(2)]=true) and Children with difficulties ([com26]=1 or 2 or 3)	From the Strength and Difficulty Questionnaire from Goodman, 2001
Measures of disruption caused to the child due to these difficulties (difficulties variable com26)	com28	Adults living with children	With their own children ([soc8(1)]=true or [soc8(2)]=true) and Children with difficulties ([com26]=1 or 2 or 3)	From the Strength and Difficulty Questionnaire from Goodman, 2001
Measures of the interference of these difficulties (difficulties variable com26) with the child's daily life, life at home, with friendships, learning at school and leisures	com29 to com33	Adults living with children	With their own children ([soc8(1)]=true or [soc8(2)]=true) and Children with difficulties ([com26]=1 or 2 or 3)	From the Strength and Difficulty Questionnaire from Goodman, 2001
Measures of the weight of these difficulties on the participant or their family	com34	Adults living with children	With their own children ([soc8(1)]=true or [soc8(2)]=true) and Children with difficulties ([com26]=1 or 2 or 3)	From the Strength and Difficulty Questionnaire from Goodman, 2001

SECTION – Foster families

Name of variable	Label	Targeted population	Additional rules	Comments
Modifications to the parent-child interactions	acc2	Foster parents		Questionnaire Ad Hoc 2 (May 2021) only Self-developed questions
Phone or socio-numerical media use to allow the child to stay in contact with their biological parent(s)	acc3, acc3a	Foster parents		Questionnaire Ad Hoc 2 (May 2021) only Self-developed questions
Impression of the child's good adaptation to the modifications to the contact details	acc4	Foster parents		Questionnaire Ad Hoc 2 (May 2021) only Self-developed questions
Participant's degree of satisfaction regarding government instored suspension measures of access rights	acc5, acc5a	Foster parents		Questionnaire Ad Hoc 2 (May 2021) only Self-developed questions
Important unaddressed aspects which the participant would like to share	acc6	Foster parents		Questionnaire Ad Hoc 2 (May 2021) only Self-developed questions Qualitative variable

SECTION - Caregivers

Name of variable	Label	Targeted population	Additional rules	Comments
Place where supported person lives	pro29	Caregivers		
Duration of caregiving relationship with an adult	pro30	Caregivers	Helped adult person ([cha5_ah2] >= 1 or [cha6_ah2] >= 1)	
Relation to helped adult	pro31	Caregivers	Helped adult person ([cha5_ah2] >= 1 or [cha6_ah2] >= 1)	
Gender of helped adult	pro32	Caregivers	Helped adult person Personne aidée adulte ([cha5_ah2] >= 1 or [cha6_ah2] >= 1)	
Medical condition of helped adult	pro33	Caregivers	Helped adult person ([cha5_ah2] >= 1 or [cha6_ah2] >= 1)	
Caregiver scale - Burden Scale for Family Caregivers	PRO (28 questions, pro1 to pro28)	Caregivers		From Gräsel, et al. 2003
Pandemic caregiving experience	pro35	Caregivers		Qualitative variable
Rural or urban caregiving experience	pro36	Caregivers		Qualitative variable
Participant's children ≤ 18 years old with disabilities	proe1	Caregivers	[cha5_ah2] >= 1 or [cha6_ah2] >= 1	
Number of children with disabilities	proe2	Caregivers	Children ≤ 18 years old with disabilities ([proe1]=1)	

Child's place of residence	proe_log	Caregivers	Children ≤ 18 years old with disabilities ([proe1]=1)
Relation between child and participant	proe3	Caregivers	Children ≤ 18 years old with disabilities ([proe1]=1)
Child's disability category	proe3b, proe3ba	Caregivers	Children ≤ 18 years old with disabilities ([proe1]=1)
Child's received diagnosis/-es	proe_dx, proe_dxa	Caregivers	Children ≤ 18 years old with disabilities ([proe1]=1)
Measure of the effect of changes made to the organisation and function of services on the participant's received support to meet their needs	proe4	Caregivers	Children ≤ 18 years old with disabilities ([proe1]=1)
Implementation by the participant, of an educational support routine for the child	proe5	Caregivers	Children ≤ 18 years old with disabilities ([proe1]=1)
Measure of the maintenance of interpersonal relationships with loved ones and entourage using communication technologies	proe6	Caregivers	Children ≤ 18 years old with disabilities ([proe1]=1)
Measure of the parent meeting the needs of the child	proe7	Caregivers	Children ≤ 18 years old with disabilities ([proe1]=1)
Measure of the impact of parents associations' suspended activities for children with disabilities or limitation of the support provided	proe8	Caregivers	Children ≤ 18 years old with disabilities ([proe1]=1)

Measure of the impact of the suspension of weekend respite services on participant's workload regarding the child and family	proe9	Caregivers	Children ≤ 18 years old with disabilities ([proe1]=1)
Level of stress due to the uncertainty of provision and availability of summer camps for the child	proe10	Caregivers	Children ≤ 18 years old with disabilities ([proe1]=1)
Measure of the met needs of the child by actors of the health and social services networks despite changes made to the services offered	proe11	Caregivers	Children ≤ 18 years old with disabilities ([proe1]=1)

SECTION –Quality of the environment

Name of variable	Label	Targeted population	Additional rules	Comments
Type of significant and persistent deficiency or disability	inc1/incb	Disabilities		
Legally blind participant	inc3	Disabilities	Disabilities regarding vision ([inc1b(1)]=true)	
Legally deaf participant	inc4	Disabilities	Disabilities regarding hearing ([inc1b(2)]=true)	
Participant considers themselves hard of hearing or deaf	inc4b	Disabilities	Disabilities regarding hearing ([inc1b(2)]=true)	

Time of onset of hearing problem	inc10	Disabilities	Disabilities regarding hearing ([inc1b(2)]=true)
Participant communication difficulties	inc5, inc5a	Disabilities	Disabilities regarding hearing ([inc1b(2)]=true)
Participant communication difficulties with others	inc6	Disabilities	Disabilities regarding hearing ([inc1b(2)]=true)
Participant's impression regarding their access to information about governmental measures	inc7, inc7a	Disabilities	Disabilities regarding hearing ([inc1b(2)]=true)
Participant's impression regarding their access to information they need	inc8, inc8a	Disabilities	Disabilities regarding hearing ([inc1b(2)]=true)
Use of a walking aid or wheelchair	inc9	Disabilities	Disabilities regarding mobility ([inc1b(3)]=true)
MQE scale	MQE (66 questions, mqe1 to mqe78)	Disabilities	

SECTION - Life habits

Name of variable	Label	Targeted population	Additional rules	Comments
Diagnosis/-es applicable to participant	dx_incapacit	Disabilities		
Protective supervision (such as the <i>Curateur public du Québec</i>)	regime_protect	Disabilities		
Level of increase of support provided to the participant due to their limitations or disabilities	q_ind_incap1	Disabilities		

Measures put in place to fight the pandemic consider the situation of people with disabilities	q_ind_incap2	Disabilities
Feeling of being more at risk of catching COVID-19	q_ind_incap17	Disabilities
Availability of necessary financial, human, and physical support	q_ind_incap3	Disabilities
Difficulties obtaining health services	q_ind_incap18	Disabilities
Use of social media as a source of information regarding the pandemic	q_ind_incap4	Disabilities
Accessibility of means of communication used by public authorities	q_ind_incap5	Disabilities
Comprehension and accessibility of information communicated by public authorities	q_ind_incap6	Disabilities
Level of agreeance with measures in place	q_ind_incap19	Disabilities
Comprehension of reasons for having these measures in place	q_ind_incap20	Disabilities
Information communicated by public authorities concern the participant	q_ind_incap7	Disabilities
The needs of people with disabilities have been met to the extent possible by public authorities	q_ind_incap8	Disabilities

Participant's level of accessibility to services and support needed	q_ind_incap9	Disabilities
Level of disturbance to activities of daily living by measures put in place by public authorities	q_ind_incap10	Disabilities
Measure of the maintenance of interpersonal relationships with entourage using communication technology	q_ind_incap11	Disabilities
Increase of social isolation due to changes in services received	q_ind_incap12	Disabilities
Measure of the impact of ceased socio-professional and community activities on participant's daily life	q_ind_incap13	Disabilities
Measures of the importance of organisms for the collective rights of handicapped people to the maintenance of services and access to information	q_ind_incap14	Disabilities
Adequate support from family and loved ones	q_ind_incap15	Disabilities
Gender differences in disabled individuals on the impact of the implementation of measures to fight the pandemic	q_ind_incap16	Disabilities
Feelings regarding the arrival of the vaccine	q_ind_incap21	Disabilities

My life habits	mhavie_XXXX# (items 1 to 32 : 5 questions each)	Disabilities	Adapted from Fougeyrollas et Noreau 2014
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SECTION - Health and social services workers

Name of variable	Label	Targeted population	Additional rules	Comments
Participant's job in health network	emp8	RSSS Actors		Up to participant 345, single choice question. As of participant 346, multiple choice questions
Working sector	emp9	RSSS Actors	social service/social worker ([emp8(2)]=true)	
Title of occupied position	emp10	RSSS Actors		
Direct customer care or services	emp11_ah2	RSSS Actors		
Work scale (questions for social service workers)	TRA (8 questions, tra1 to tra8)	RSSS Actors		Self-developed questions by the CRUJeF
Beliefs scale	CRO (12 questions, cro1 to cro6 and cro11 to cro16)	RSSS Actors		
Change scale	CHAN (10 questions, chan1 to chan10)	RSSS Actors		
Measures of burnout - from Maslach Burnout Inventory	fat1 and fat2	RSSS Actors		From Maslach, et al. 1996 (selected questions)
Motivation at work scale	mot1 to mot6	RSSS Actors		From Snyder, 1996: variable valid as of participant 271
Participant's worries regarding caring for patients diagnosed with COVID-19 or susceptible to being so	avis1	RSSS Actors		Qualitative variable

Participant's relevant training in the context of the pandemic	avis2	RSSS Actors	Qualitative variable
Important element that could have improved the participant's well-being	avis3	RSSS Actors	Qualitative variable
Examples of processes, changes in work organisation, interventions, favorable policies or any other positive element in the participant's work field	avis3b	RSSS Actors	Qualitative variable

SECTION - Final questions

Name of variable	Label	Targeted population	Additional rules	Comments
Participant sharing a testimonial or lived experience	avis6	All		Qualitative variable
Complete Zip code	zip2	All		From Ad Hoc 3 questionnaire (May 2022) onward
Past or future move	log8 et log9	All		From Ad Hoc 3 questionnaire (May 2022) onward
Individual having responded to questions	lit1	All		From Ad Hoc 3 questionnaire (May 2022) onward

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